

Structural and antimicrobial studies of some newly synthesized mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

R. C. Sharma*, P. P. Giri and D. Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Khandari Road, Agra-282 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dev_kumar26@indiatimes.com

Manuscript received 12 March 2010, revised 19 July 2010, accepted 20 July 2010

Abstract : Four new mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with 2-furylglyoxal-2-amino thiophenol (FGATP) and diphenyl amine-2-hydroxy-2'-carboxylic acid (DPHC) were synthesized and characterized by their melting point determination of recrystallised samples, running TLC for single spot, elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic measurements, IR, ¹H NMR and UV spectral data. All the synthesized compounds were screened for antimicrobial activities against two bacteria, *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), and two fungi, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Metal complexes exhibit several fold increase in their antimicrobial activity in comparison to that of the constituting ligand fragments as determined by Serial Dilution Method.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, spectral studies, antimicrobial activities.

Introduction

Transition metals in the form of their complexes are responsible for several biological transformations and redox reactions in life processes¹. They also find applications in analytical², industrial^{3,4}, pharmaceutical⁵ and medicinal⁶ fields. A survey of literature reveals that the compounds having nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur as donor sites behave as anticancer⁷, antiviral⁸, antimicrobial⁹ agents. In addition to above, mixed ligand complexes of metals have been reported as effective biocidal agents¹⁰⁻¹². These facts prompted us to synthesize some new mixed ligand complexes of bivalent metal ions of biological importance to study the combined antimicrobial activities of the ligands in conjunction with metal ions.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of complexes (Table 1) suggested their (1 : 1 : 1) M : L₁ : L₂ stoichiometry and the conductivity measurements reveal their non-electrolytical nature.

The ligand FGATP revealed characteristic IR bands at 1620 cm⁻¹ (>C=N), 1490 cm⁻¹ (furan ring breathing vibrations), 1735 cm⁻¹ (>C=O stretching vibrations) and 2650 cm⁻¹ (-SH thiophenol stretching vibrations). A negative shift in the band positions of >C=N and >C=O stretching frequency by 30-40 cm⁻¹ and formation of

new bands around 540-520 cm⁻¹ and 450-430 cm⁻¹ due to M-O and M-N bonds¹³ respectively indicates the coordination of ligand to metal through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. The disappearance of the -SH stretching vibrations of the ligand due to deprotonation and the appearance of a new band around 340-320 cm⁻¹, due to formation of M-S bond¹³, further confirm the coordination of the ligand to the metal through sulphur atom. The ligand DPHC exhibits IR bands at 1590 cm⁻¹ (-NH bending vibration), 3580 cm⁻¹ (-OH phenolic) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) and 3480 cm⁻¹ (-OH) of carboxylic group. In the IR spectra of metal complexes, the -NH band has shifted to negative side by 20-40 cm⁻¹, which indicates its involvement in bonding with metal. The disappearance of the band due to the carboxylic proton and the development of a new band in the region 540-520 cm⁻¹, indicate the deprotonation of -COOH group and its coordination to metal ion through oxygen forming M-O bond. The presence of coordinated water molecules within coordination sphere of all complexes is supported by the appearance of broad bands in the region 3500-3400 and 840-810 cm⁻¹ due to stretching and bending vibrations of -OH group respectively.

¹H NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ solvent using TMS as an internal standard.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of ligands and their metal complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
					C	H	N	S	M
1.	DPHC	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	Brown	144	67.89 (68.59)	3.9 (6.59)	5.69 (4.30)	- (6.11)	-
2.	FGATP	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ NS	Black	98	61.87 (62.34)	3.79 (3.89)	5.94 (6.06)	13.54 (13.85)	-
3.	Co ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ S.Co	Dark brown	326	57.75 (58.02)	4.33 (3.67)	3.54 (5.41)	5.62 (6.19)	10.57 (11.40)
4.	Ni ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ S.Ni	Blakish brown	316	59.76 (58.06)	3.56 (3.66)	4.34 (5.42)	5.62 (6.20)	10.59 (11.42)
5.	Cu ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ S.Cu	Black	320	56.18 (57.52)	4.47 (3.64)	3.58 (5.36)	5.44 (5.36)	11.29 (12.18)
6.	Zn ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₂ S.Zn	Brown	305	56.86 (57.31)	3.51 (3.63)	4.29 (5.34)	5.47 (5.34)	11.86 (12.51)

The ligand FGATP shows two multiplets in the region δ 7.70–7.81 ppm and 7.42–7.64 ppm due to furyl ring protons and aromatic ring protons respectively, a singlet at δ 7.89 ppm due to $>CH=N$ proton and a singlet at δ 1.78 ppm due to -SH proton. The ligand DPHC shows a singlet at δ 11.24 ppm due to -COOH proton, a multiplet in the region δ 7.40–7.80 ppm due to aromatic protons, a singlet at δ 8.32 ppm due to -NH- proton and a singlet at δ 5.38 ppm due to -OH proton.

¹H NMR spectra of complexes show two multiplets in the region δ 7.73–7.94 ppm and 7.36–7.70 ppm due to furyl ring protons and aromatic ring protons respectively. The singlets due to protons of $>CH=N$, -NH, and -OH have shifted to downfield in the range δ 7.97–8.12, 8.38–8.42 and 5.45–5.52 ppm respectively, due to decrease electron density and deshielding of protons, as a result of participation of the $>CH=N$, -NH and -OH groups in coordination^{14,15}. The singlets due to -COOH and -SH proton have disappeared in the spectra of complexes which indicate deprotonation of these groups during coordination with metallic ions^{16,17}.

The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} mixed ligand complex showed three absorption bands at 885.8, 615.8 and 382.4 nm arising due to octahedral field transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{2g}$ respectively¹⁸. The magnetic susceptibility value of Cu^{II} was found 1.86 BM which is in close agreement with the octahedral geometry.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complex reveals bands at 897.8, 560.9 and 400.9 nm corresponding to the tran-

sition ${}^2A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) respectively suggesting an octahedral geometry¹⁹. The magnetic susceptibility of Ni^{II} complex was found 3.19 BM which is very close to the value for its octahedral environment.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex exhibits bands at 862.0, 627.9, 526.7 nm corresponding to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) respectively indicating an octahedral geometry²⁰. The magnetic susceptibility value for this complex was found 4.85 BM, which is further in conformity for an octahedral geometry. As expected, the Zn complex was found diamagnetic in nature.

On the basis of elemental analyses, IR, ¹H NMR and electronic spectral studies, it is confirmed that all the M^{II} complexes have octahedral geometry as presented in the Figure.

where $M^{2+} = Co^{2+}, Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}$ and Zn^{2+}

Fig. 1. Probable structure of complexes.

The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration values of the compounds were determined by the comparing the growth

of spores in different test tubes having the different concentrations under optimum aseptic experimental conditions. A comparative study of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration values (Table 2) in general infers that the antimicrobial activity of metal complexes is many fold increased in comparison to their ligands. An enhancement in the antimicrobial activity of all metal complexes may be due to the faster diffusion of the lyophobic metal complexes to lipids through the cell membrane and their combined activity effect²¹.

on Jasco spectrophotometer (Model Rx-100) in KBr medium. The electronic spectra of mixed ligand complexes were recorded in dry DMF or DMSO at room temperature on Shimadzu Digital Double Beam spectrophotometer (Model UV 150-150.20).

(a) *Synthesis of furan-2-glyoxal* : In a 250 ml, 2 neck interjoint round bottom flask fitted with water condenser and a thermometer, 1.13 g (0.01 mol) SeO₂, 20 ml ethanol and 2 ml water were taken. The mixture was heated at 50–55 °C with continuous stirring till SeO₂ was dis-

Table 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values in molar concentration (10^{-5}) of ligands and metal complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Bacteria		Fungi	
		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
1.	DPHC	23.83	23.83	12.91	12.91
2.	FGATP	21.64	21.64	10.82	10.82
3.	Co ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	5.67	5.67	5.67	5.67
4.	Ni ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	5.17	5.17	5.17	5.17
5.	Cu ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	4.63	4.63	4.63	4.63
6.	Zn ^{II} -FGATP-DPHC	4.91	4.91	4.91	4.91

Experimental

C, H and N analyses were carried out on Carlo Erba Micro Analyser (Model 1106) and sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ by standard method²². Copper, nickel, cobalt and zinc contents in their metal complexes were estimated by their pyridine complex¹⁸ formation method, Cu as [Cu(C₆H₅N₂)₂](SCN)₂, Ni as [Ni(C₆H₅N₂)₂](SCN)₂, Co as [Co(C₆H₅N₂)₂](SCN)₂ and Zn as [Zn(C₆H₅N₂)₂](SCN)₂. In all these estimations, a known quantity of metal complex was heated with 10 ml 1 : 1, mixture of conc. sulphuric acid and conc. nitric acid until whole of the organic matter was decomposed. Then acid mixture was evaporated and residue was dissolved in 50 ml distilled water. The solution thus obtained was filtered, diluted with 25 ml water and treated with an excess of ammonium thiocyanate and pure pyridine to get desire metal complex. The obtained precipitate was digested, filtered and washed with water, followed by few drops of alcohol and then with ether and finally it was dried in a desiccator over P₂O₅. The molar conductance measurements were made in 10⁻³ M solution of complexes in dry DMF or DMSO using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge. The magnetic susceptibilities of complexes were determined by using Gouy's method. IR spectra were recorded

solved completely. 1.29 g (0.01 mol, 1.31 ml) 2-acetyl furan was added in one lot to the above solution and refluxed over a water bath for about 7 h. The reduced Se metal was removed by filtration through a fluted filter paper and the solvent of the filtrate was removed by distillation through a short vigreux column. A yellow coloured furan-2-glyoxal was obtained (b.p. 65 ± 0.1 ° C).

(b) *Synthesis of furan-2-glyoxal-aminothiophenol (FGATP)* : Furyl-2-glyoxal (1.24 g, 0.01 mol), dissolved in 20 ml ethanol and 2-amino thiophenol (1.28 ml, 0.01 mol), dissolved in 15 ml ethanol were mixed and refluxed for about 6 h. On cooling in refrigerator, obtained black crystals were filtered and washed with ethanol followed by ether and recrystallized from ethanol. Finally, the obtained product was dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

(c) *Synthesis of diphenyl amine-2-hydroxyl-2'-carboxylic acid (DPHC)* : *o*-Chloro benzoic acid (1.57 g, 0.01 mol) and *o*-aminophenol (1.09 g, 0.1 mol) were taken in 75 ml distilled water in a round bottom flask. This mixture was made slightly alkaline with aqueous solutions of K₂CO₃ and little amount of copper oxide was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 5 h. 1.0 g activated charcoal was added to the mixture and again

refluxed for 1 h. It was filtered, concentrated to ¼ of its original volume and acidified with dil. HCl. Obtained brown precipitate was filtered, recrystallized from ethanol and dried.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : An ethanolic solution of the ligand (DPHC), prepared by dissolving 0.12 g (0.0005 mol) DPHC in 10 ml ethanol, was mixed with 15 ml solution of FGATP (0.12 g, 0.0005 mol in 15 ml of ethanol) in a 250 ml of round bottom flask and ethanolic solutions of metal acetate (0.0005 mol) [0.099 g, (AcO)₂Cu.H₂O/0.125 g, (AcO)₂Co.4H₂O/0.109 g (AcO)₂Zn.2H₂O] were added. To this 1–2 ml NH₃ solution was added to adjust its pH 6–7 (tested by pH paper). The obtained mixture was refluxed for about 3–4 h. The products thus obtained were filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by with ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Antimicrobial studies : The antimicrobial studies of the synthesized compounds were screened against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve) and *Echerichia coli* (Gram –ve) and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by adopting Serial Dilution Method²³ in suitable nutrient medium (6.0 g peptone, 3.0 g yeast extract, 1.5 g beef extract, 1.5 g agar only for slant and 1.0 g dextrose in one litre distilled water for bacteria and 10.0 g peptone, 20.5 g agar only for slant 20.0 g dextrose in one litre distilled water for fungi). Graded diluted solutions of the test compounds with the micro organisms under examination using aseptic conditions were incubated at their optimum temperature (37 °C for 24 h in case of bacteria and at 28 °C for 96 h in case of fungi) in a B.O.D. incubator.

References

1. R. E. Feeney, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1961, **34**, 196.
2. Renu Ahuja and K. Dwivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 119.
3. F. Bland, *Nature*, 1951, **168**, 516.
4. G. Dgniriadhis and A. Chamsin, *Chem. Anal. Peris*, 1971, **53**, 31.
5. S. Carotti, G. Marcon, M. Marussich, T. Mazzei, L. Messori, E. Mini and P. Orioli, *Chem. Biolog. Interac.*, 2000, **29**, 125.
6. A. M. Chadooshi, *Farm Polaska*, 1964, **22**, 37.
7. M. Mathew, G. J. Palemic and G. R. Clark, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 446.
8. P. A. French and E. J. Blang, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 585.
9. J. D. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 5.
10. G. Petering, H. H. Buskrik and G. G. Underwood, *Cancer Res.*, 1964, **64**, 367.
11. D. S. Rao and M. C. Ganorkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 217.
12. D. Kumar, Jaggi Lal and V. Kumar, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 2009, **79A(I)**, 17.
13. K. Nakamoto, "Infra Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1970.
14. J. M. Daw, W. Hanerson and B. K. Nicholson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, **45**, 87.
15. A. M. Hassaan, M. A. Khalifa and A. K. Shehata, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1995, **104**, 121.
16. S. O. Podunavac-Kuzmanovic, V. M. Leovac, N. U. Perisic-Janjic, J. Rogan and Balas, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **64**, 381.
17. A. Z. El-Sonbati, *Spectroscopy Lett.*, 1997, **30**, 459.
18. A. B. P. Lever and E. Mantovani, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 40.
19. T. D. Chaudhari and S. S. Selensis, *Bull. Hoffkings Inst.*, 1976, **4**, 85.
20. W. K. Kusker and M. S. Hussain, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1416.
21. J. A. Jahangirdar, B. G. Patil and B. R. Havinale, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 924.
22. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman's, London, 1968.
23. D. F. Spooner and A. Sykes, "Methods in Microbiology", Academic Press, London, 1972.